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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The Transsmed project, funded through the Erasmus+ programme, focuses on establishing a competency-based education system through simulations in primary healthcare, aimed at increasing patient safety in life-threatening situations. The project started in September 2022 and will run for three years. The project partners include the Faculty of Medicine in Skopje, the Faculty of Medicine in Zagreb, the Health Center in Zagreb, and the Health Center Ljubljana. A key objective of the project is the development of a simulation center in North Macedonia that will offer training for doctors and nurses at the primary healthcare level.

Materials and Methods: As part of the project, several workshops have been conducted. One of these was the "BLS" (Basic Life Support) workshop, which was attended by 427 participants. Additionally, the "Anaphylactic Shock" workshop was held from October to December 2024, consisting of 34 workshops with 134 participants. Also, there were 12 workshops with 120 sixth-year medical students, during January – February 2025 there were 9 workshops for community pharmacists with 45 participants.

Results: The general evaluation of the workshops revealed exceptionally high ratings, with 99.6% of participants rating the quality of the workshops as excellent. An important aspect of the education involves integrating simulation-based learning into the standard curriculum. The results have been outstanding: over 90% of students were able to promptly recognize an anaphylactic shock and take appropriate action (Simons et al., 2011). Simulation-based education has been rated as the most effective and realistic approach to improving responses to emergency healthcare situations in everyday work at primary healthcare facilities.

Conclusion: Additionally, the Transsmed project included the training of advanced instructors from North Macedonia at the Ljubljana Simulation Center. These advanced instructors are now equipped to train basic instructors and will work at a high level in all domains of simulation education in primary healthcare. The Transsmed project emphasizes the importance of continuous education through simulations, which is crucial for improving healthcare quality and reducing deaths due to improperly managed emergency situations. The establishment of a simulation center at the primary healthcare level in Skopje will ensure ongoing training for healthcare professionals and contribute to increased patient safety. By the end of 2024, 4,701 participants were trained at the Skopje Simulation Center, further demonstrating the success of the program.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Transsmed project, simulations, primary healthcare

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Simons, F. E. R., Arduoso, L. R. F., Bilo, M. B., El-Gamal, Y. M., Ledford, D. K., Ring, J., ... & Sheikh, A. (2011). World Allergy Organization guidelines for the assessment and management of anaphylaxis. *World Allergy Organization Journal*, 4(2), 13–37. <https://doi.org/10.1097/WOX.0b013e318211496c>

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